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KRIVIČNOPRAVNA ZAŠTITA DECE – ŽRTAVA TRGOVINE LJUDIMA

Trgovina decom je jedan od najokrutnijih zločina protiv čovečnosti i drugih dobara zaštićenih međunarodnim pravom. S obzirom da se trgovci ljudima koriste raznim manipulacijama, lažima, obmanama, ali i pretnjama i nasiljem prema žrtvama, deca su najranjivija grupa trgovine ljudima. Trgovina decom inkriminisana je krivičnim zakonikom kao kvalifikovani oblik krivičnog dela trgovine ljudima. Decom se trguje radi eksploatacije njihova rada, prinudnog rada, vršenja krivičnih dela, seksualne eksploatacije i prostitucije, prosjačenja, upotrebe u pornografske svrhe, uspostavljanja ropskog ili njemu sličnog odnosa, radi oduzimanja organa ili dela tela ili radi korišćenja u oružanim sukobima, ali i radi usvojenja. Trgovina decom radi usvojenja predstavlja posebno krivično delo. Rad sadrži analizu nacionalnog i međunarodnog pravnog okvira za suzbijanje trgovine decom uz analizu sudske prakse. Kroz istraživanje obuhvaćeni su svi oblici i vrste iskorišćavanja dece u izvršenju krivičnih dela trgovine ljudima i trgovine decom radi usvojenja. U zaključnim razmatranjima je, shodno analizi i istraživanju, navedena ocena stanja de lege lata te su dati predlozi de lege ferenda s ciljem suzbijanja eksploatacije dece, kao i trgovine decom radi usvojenja.

Ključne reči: Trgovina decom, eksploatacija dece, trgovina decom radi usvojenja, krivičnoppravna zaštita, nacionalni i međunarodni pravni okvir.

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CRIMINAL LAW PROTECTION OF CHILDREN: VICTIMS OF HUMAN TRAFFICKING

Child trafficking is one of the most cruel crimes against humanity and other goods protected by international law. Given that traffickers use various manipulations, lies, deception, threats as well as violence against victims, children are the most vulnerable group in human trafficking. In the Republic of Serbia, child trafficking is criminalized by the Criminal Code as a qualified form of the criminal offence of human trafficking. Children are trafficked for the purpose of labour exploitation, forced labor, commission of criminal offenses, sexual exploitation, prostitution, begging, pornographic purposes, slavery or servitude, removing organs or body parts, for use in armed conflicts, but also for the purpose of adoption. Trafficking in children for the purpose of adoption is a separate criminal offense. The paper contains an analysis of the national and international legal framework for combating child trafficking, accompanied by an analysis of case law. The research covers all forms and types of exploitation of children in the commission of criminal acts of human trafficking and child trafficking for adoption. Based on the research and analysis, in the concluding remarks, the author provides an assessment of the situation *de lege lata* and proposals *de lege ferenda* aimed at combating the exploitation of children as well as trafficking in children for adoption.

Keywords: trafficking in children, exploitation of children, trafficking in children for adoption, criminal protection, national and international legal framework.